

ART STUDIES

TEACHING AND REFLECTIONS ON THE SINICIZATION OF DOUBLE BASS

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Abstract

Beginning in the first half of the 20th century, China's first batch of double bass teachers, faced with a shortage of literature and resources, persevered with great resilience to pioneer the development of double bass teaching. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, during numerous cultural exchanges between China and the Soviet Union, lectures and performances by Soviet double bass experts, led by the principal double bassist of the Soviet Grand Theatre Symphony Orchestra and Professor Kirov of the Moscow Conservatory, had a profound impact on the teaching of double bass in China. Drawing from my own teaching and performance experiences, I will share some specific professional insights.

Keywords: double bass, sinicized education, orchestra, teaching experience.

Since the first half of the 20th century, China's first batch of double bass teachers, faced with a scarcity of literature and resources, have persevered with great resilience, pioneering the development of double bass teaching. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, during numerous cultural exchanges between China and the Soviet Union, lectures and performances by Soviet double bass experts, led by the principal double bassist of the Soviet Grand Theatre Symphony Orchestra and Professor Kinovich of the Moscow Conservatory, had a profound impact on China's double bass teaching. As time evolved, following the reform and opening up, the arrival of numerous foreign masters brought new perspectives to China's double bass

community. The influx of a vast amount of sheet music and literature significantly elevated the standard of double bass teaching in China. Since then, the education of double bass has flourished, gradually moving towards professionalization, standardization, and systematization.

Teaching Professional Skills for Double Bass The teaching of professional skills for the double bass is the most fundamental and also one of the most important courses in double bass teaching. The training of professional skills directly affects the performer's control over intonation, as well as their handling of tone, dynamics, playing techniques, and expression of musical content.

(1) Playing Posture As a double bass teacher in a professional conservatory, the first thing I mention when teaching new students is the aspect of playing posture. At that time, the students present were deeply confused, and some even directly asked whether it was really necessary to start with the most basic bow holding as a professional student. However, this seemingly simple question is actually difficult to understand and even more challenging to execute. Students' understanding of playing posture generally remains at the level of just holding the bow and instrument steadily, unaware that this has already planted important hidden dangers for their sound state and even musical expression during performance. In fact, the term "holding steadily" is only half correct. On this basis, students need to know how to "hold properly", and even understand the convenience brought by the standard playing posture. Only in this way can students truly remind themselves to maintain the most correct and reasonable posture for holding the instrument and bow at all times.

1. Holding the Double Bass The holding posture for the double bass can generally be divided into two types: standing holding and sitting holding. These two different postures can be applied to different performance occasions, and even different performance styles and orchestra configurations. Therefore, both types of holding posture should be mastered. Among them, standing holding requires students to stand with their feet shoulder-width apart, with the instrument in contact with their body at a moderate angle, and leaning the instrument against their body. Sitting holding, on the other hand, requires students to sit only on two-thirds of the bench, leaning forward, and maintaining a reasonable support angle between the instrument and the body. In summary, students should strive to keep the instrument and themselves steady, and on this basis, maintain a unity between the instrument and the player, allowing the whole body to better exert force and transmit it to the bow-holding arm.

2. Holding the Bow In the violin family, the bow for the double bass is more diverse than that of other instruments, and can be divided into German bows and French bows, with corresponding holding methods also divided into German and French categories. They originated from different regions and have deep historical origins. Usually, each performer only uses one type of bow throughout their lifetime. Although these two types of bows each have their own advantages and disadvantages, with proper training, either type of bow can achieve good playing effects. When holding the bow, students should always keep their hands relaxed to avoid stiff and rigid playing, which lacks flexibility. The thumb and middle finger are responsible for holding the bow steadily; the index finger and little finger are responsible for adjusting the bow pressure and string touch angle; the ring finger assists the other fingers. Overall, good and relaxed coordination among the arm, wrist, and fingers is crucial for holding the bow.

(II) Bowing is the most crucial aspect of double bass playing. Only by mastering the bowing motion proficiently and correctly, reasonably controlling the relationship between the bow and the string, and arranging the bowing technique appropriately can one play music coherently and smoothly, fully expressing

inner emotions. During basic training, students should first practice the method of playing with divided bows in a relaxed state. As their proficiency increases, they should gradually incorporate training in more bowing techniques such as legato bowing and spiccato bowing. When playing, students must ensure smoothness and consistency in bow speed. At the same time, they should always perceive the transmission of force during playing, allowing the force to originate from the back, passing through the shoulders, upper arms, lower arms, wrists, fingers, and ultimately to the bow. On the other hand, the contact angle between the bow and the string should always be maintained at a 90-degree angle, and the contact point between the bow and the string should be accurately identified to achieve better sound effects.

(III) Among various stringed instruments, the fingerboard of the double bass is the longest and widest, and the distance between tones is also farther than that of other stringed instruments. Because of this, the double bass requires the most frequent changing of fingers, and the distance of palm movement during finger changing is also extremely long. This places higher demands on students' speed and accuracy during finger changing. In terms of finger position training, after students have mastered various finger changing techniques such as same finger changing and easy finger changing, the most important thing to focus on is the coordination between the left and right hands. Among them, the left hand's finger changing should be slightly earlier than the right hand's bowing, while ensuring speed and accuracy, and should be done at the bow change or the breath mark of the phrase. This can effectively avoid the occurrence of noise. The training of thumb position should be gradual. After fully familiarizing oneself with the transition and playing from the half position to the seventh position, training can be carried out. During practice, students should first find the optimal support points for the violin and the body to fully free up the left arm and fingers, so that the thumb can freely move on the fingerboard. On the other hand, since playing at high positions is technically more difficult than at basic positions, students should listen carefully to the pitch accuracy, practice slowly and repeatedly until finding the most accurate pitch.

(IV) Timbre Generally speaking, the timbre of the double bass stands out among the violin family. Due to the extremely long strings of the double bass, it produces more harmonics when vibrating, resulting in a deep, powerful, and mellow timbre. In orchestras, the double bass serves as the foundation of the bass section with its distinctive sound. In more solo and ensemble pieces, the expressiveness of the double bass is even richer, and its timbre appears more varied. In fact, the variation in the timbre of the double bass is determined by different playing techniques. In instrument playing, the choice and application of different techniques can bring about different sound effects and stylistic characteristics. On one hand, the point of contact with the bow on the string greatly affects the variation in the timbre of the double bass: if played at 1/2 of the distance between the fingerboard and the bridge, the sound will be mellow and solid; if played at a lower position, the sound will be dry and hard; if played at a higher position, the timbre will be softer and darker. Therefore, it

is essential to choose the appropriate point of contact with the bow based on the different characteristics of the musical passages. When the left hand is above the fingerboard, the right hand should also be at a higher point of contact with the string; when the left hand is below the fingerboard, the right hand should also be at a lower point of contact with the string. Of course, the aforementioned two special timbres are also used in special musical passages, such as playing harmonics close to the bridge, which is extremely expressive. In addition, the speed and pressure of the bow in the right hand also affect the timbre. On the other hand, the amplitude and frequency of the left hand's vibrato also influence the variation in timbre. The choice of vibrato style mainly depends on the style of music. For example, in more traditional classical works, the amplitude of the vibrato should be controlled, and the bow should be moved smoothly forward, making the music flow well; in romantic works, the amplitude and frequency of the double bass's vibrato should be increased.

II. Teaching of Double Bass Theory Courses. The teaching of double bass theory courses is a crucial subject that students urgently need to strengthen after they have initially mastered general double bass playing skills. The study of theory courses can enable students to gain a deeper understanding of the double bass music they play, and also provide them with clear directions and goals during practice.

(1) For double bass students who have entered professional music schools, basic intonation is something that every student can master through theoretical intonation training. However, due to the interference caused by extremely long strings and a large instrument body during performance, students should adopt a rational and theoretical approach to intonation training to ensure accurate pitch when playing difficult double bass melodic passages.

(II) Theoretical free tempo training: For double bass students who have entered professional conservatories, playing at a constant speed is relatively easy to achieve, but mastering the more flexible tempo control is a key aspect that requires focused training. For the incredibly deep double bass, emotional playing requires extremely delicate tempo variations to convey.

III. Teaching of Double Bass Ensemble Course Since the 17th century, the double bass has been widely used in large Western orchestra ensembles. Together with the cello, it supports the deepest bass section of the entire orchestra's sound or serves as the foundation for the rhythm of the music, playing an important role in the orchestra. Even in China's national orchestras and American jazz bands, the double bass is also indispensable.

(I) **Good Coordination** In the orchestra ensemble class for double bass, it is most important to exercise auditory coordination. Firstly, students should listen to the melodic lines of each other's parts and coordinate with them. Compared to middle and high-pitched instruments, the rich harmonics of the double bass make its pitch more ambiguous, especially when playing in the low-pitched range.

(II) **Music Handling in Double Bass Orchestra Ensembles** In double bass orchestra ensembles, whether it's the supporting part in the low-pitched range, the

plucked part serving as rhythmic support, or even the loud high-pitched melodic part, each player holds utmost importance, as they all influence the performance effect of the orchestra. However, no player can elevate their performance above the ensemble effect; their performance is merely a part of the orchestra's sound. It can be said that music handling and character shaping in orchestra ensembles are far more challenging than in solo performances.

After decades of vicissitudes, with the joint efforts of both new and experienced teachers, China's professional double bass teaching has achieved certain accomplishments. The teaching system of double bass is being improved, the curriculum is being perfected, and the faculty is also becoming stronger. A large number of double bass literature created by local teachers have made outstanding contributions to the development of China's double bass industry. Of course, while rejoicing, we should also see that there are still many issues to be improved in double bass teaching. The author believes that under such teaching methods, students' double bass playing skills, research ability on sheet music, aesthetic thinking on music, and band ensemble skills can all be improved. At the same time, the author also hopes that the teaching methods described in the article can also help and inspire the further advancement of the systematization process of double bass teaching in China.

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